

Research on Online Translation Practice Platform under the Guidance of China's "Mass Entrepreneurship and Innovation" Policy

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ABSTRACT: In order to deepen China's foreign exchanges and meet market needs, training translators requires closer integration of translation theory and translation practice, and emphasis on the cultivation of applied translators. Relying on the rise of China's "Internet + Education" new business mode and the support of the "mass entrepreneurship and innovation" national policy, this research plans to build a translation practice cloud platform focusing on serving MTI students' translation practices to help students integrate with the industry as soon as possible, and improve the quality of MTI training.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurship and Innovation; "Internet Plus"; Translation Practices

I. INTRODUCTION

Since 2007, the establishment of the MTI professional degree has cultivated a large number of professional translators in China, and to a certain extent has solved the problem of the ever-increasing demand for translators in the market. However, currently, there are still many problems remained in MTI education, such as unclear concept of cultivating and learning goals, unused practice bases and lack of practice for students. Meanwhile, students are also lack of career planning and professional knowledge of translation which lead to low social recognition. There are many problems such as the inadequate integration of internal and external knowledge of the profession ^[1]. In contrast, the translation talent training system of American universities has been relatively mature after decades of practice and development, which is mainly reflected in the continuity of translation needs, the flexibility of direction settings, the diversity of curriculum settings, and the systematic nature of translation studies ^[2]. And other aspects, American colleges and universities pay attention to the cultivation of applied MTI talents, and emphasize the combination of translation theory and specific translation practice. From the training direction to the curriculum setting, they are all aligned with market needs. Therefore, Chinese colleges and universities need to strengthen the planning and guidance of MTI, construct a mode for training translation talents with distinctive characteristics, improve the quality of training translation talents, and enable MTI students to have obvious practical characteristics. MTI online translation practice platform can connect both schools and the market, helping to cultivate the translation practice capabilities of MTI students. Therefore, the way to improve the construction and operation mechanism of the MTI graduate online translation practice platform, provide MTI with rich practical experience, and at the same time meet the translation needs of enterprises, is a major issue for the healthy development of MTI.

II. RESEARCH PURPOSE

The study is an applied research under the tide of China's MTI education reform. Relying on big data and technology-driven, through cooperation with enterprises, it aims to train MTI students' translation practice capabilities, including providing simulation practice for translation, revision, project manager, technical and terminology specialist in a variety of language service industry and also

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offers useful exploration for the effective connection of application technology, translation technology and education technology in the language service industry. This study explores the construction and operating mechanism of the online translation practice platform for MTI graduate students in Chinese colleges and universities with business characteristics, which can provide MTI students with rich practical experience and meet the translation needs of enterprises at the same time. With the background of business colleges and universities, we can provide professional counterpart targeted services for companies with business translation needs, distinctive features and application value; translation tasks are carried out in the form of translation projects, which can achieve efficient and high-quality translations and satisfy the market's needs.

Since students are one of the target groups of the platform in the MTI online translation practice platform, the platform provides students with real translation materials, which will improve students' translation practice capabilities. At the same time, each member of the translation team has different subject backgrounds, including translation majors, linguistics majors, and computer majors. The structure is reasonable, the division of labor is clear, and each of them performs their duties, which helps to ensure the quality of translation. Through a sound management model and streamlined the organization, the efficient operation of the platform can be promoted. At the same time, building a website with the advantage of "Internet +" is conducive to playing an active role in the era of "mass entrepreneurship and innovation".

III. CURRENT SITUATION OF CHINESE TRANSLATION PLATFORMS

The rapid development of computer technology and network environment has led to the rapid update and dissemination of information, and a spurt growth of translation needs requires that translation methods must pursue faster translation speed and higher quality when dealing with the high-volume and multi-lingual translation tasks^[3]. With the rise of the "Internet + education" in China, mobile Internet technology has made continuous progress, voice recognition, translation technology and translation platform technology have been continuously developed, and translation tools have also shifted from local to networked^[4].

Some language service organizations and localization service provider have begun to apply cloud computing technology to the translation industry to build a translation cloud platform that can meet the increasing needs of users.

According to the resources competing for each platform, China's domestic translation technology cloud platforms can be divided into four categories, namely, translation trading platforms, translation producing platforms, translation corpus data platforms, and artificial intelligence machine translation platforms^[5].

(1) Translation Trading Platforms

The translation trading platform is an online third-party trading security assurance platform that connects language service providers and customers to ensure the safety and integrity of both parties in transactions. According to the survey, there are only a few trading practice platforms in China's domestic market at present, such as "woordee.com" (a translation platform under the Shi Yi Bao), "zuodao.com" (a platform under Alibaba), "Wittrans.com", "easytep.com" and so on.

(2) Translation Producing Platforms

The well-known translation production platforms in China include Tmxmall YiCAT, Yima.com, and Yunyike. Take Tmxmall YiCAT as an example, it is an online translation management platform that establishes a fully automated, scientific and streamlined translation management model for freelance translators, translation companies and corporate translation departments.

(3) Translation Corpus Data Platforms

Corpus refers to a large number of text collections. After data cleaning, alignment and other processing, corpus is a precious resource for language research and application. It is also a warehouse for storing corpus, which is collected and stored in a computer on a large scale according to certain linguistic principles and specific language research purposes by using computer technology. The main corpora data platforms in China are Tmxmall and UTH international.

(4) Machine Translation Platform

Machine translation, also known as automatic translation, is a process in which the computer translates the natural language in the form of text or speech from the source language to the target language through processing. Since 2015, Neural Machine Translation

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(NMT) technology, which is derived from deep learning technology, has developed rapidly and started to be applied. China's machine translation platforms include Baidu Translation, Youdao Translation, Sogou Translation, and "Xunfei Voice Cloud Computing" platform, while tech giants such as Tencent and Ali are also stepping up their research and development of machine translation products, making their mark in the field of machine translation.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

Based on the above-mentioned MTI cultivating situation in universities and the development status of translation platforms in China, we can find that there is no platform in the market focusing on MTI students' translation practice. In combination with the rise of the new business mode of "Internet + education", this study intends to build a translation practice cloud platform with "translation team" as working unit and "translation project" as project operation method, which will help the majority of MTI students in China obtain translation practice as well as part-time translation opportunities .

(1) The Nature of Translation Practice Cloud Platform

First, "project team system" is adopted in the implementation of translation tasks in this study. The team includes MTI students with a business background and requires students to pass at least CATTI Three. Teachers with profound translation theory background and rich experience serve as team instructors to provide translation guidance for students' translation, which also provides opportunities for MTI teachers with some translation practical experience. The team also includes professional translators with at least two years of translation experience, who have expertise mainly in the field of business translation and are responsible for reviewing and giving feedback on the students' translations. In this way, translation theory and practice can be effectively combined to ensure the quality of translation and meet the requirements of enterprises.

Second, the target market of this study is mainly MTI students in Chinese business colleges and universities, aiming at providing professional business translation. The platform provides professional and targeted services for enterprises with business translation needs. It mainly provides Chinese small and medium-sized enterprises with business text translation, including business advertisements, business letters, business invitation letters, meeting minutes and other texts, so it has distinct characteristics and application value.

Third, the media of this study is an Internet platform designed and built by ourselves. In the context of the booming development of e-commerce in China, one side of the cloud platform is an enterprise with business translation needs, and the other end is connected with students who need translation practice. The official website is used as the main trading platform and the Wechat public account is used as the auxiliary. We plan to adopt the operation mode of online ordering, translation and delivery, which is convenient and efficient and time-saving.

(2) Operation Situation

The translation cloud platform in this study will have one general responsible person and two deputy responsible persons under four departments, namely, Personnel Department, Technology Department, Marketing Department and Translation Department. Each department will have another responsible person who is responsible for the operation and management of the department. The translation department is the main department which is composed of professional translators, tutors and a number of MTI students. A translation task will run as follows: the first group is the translation group, and students complete the first draft translation after placing an order on the website. The second group is the proofreading group, composed of instructors and professional translators. Students submit the first draft to the instructor for first review, and the teacher gives feedback to the students for revision. The revised article will submitted to the professional translator for the second review, and the final draft is formed after the revision and sent to customers through the platform. The second groups can be responsible for several first group. (The operation flow see Figure 1)

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Chart 1: operation flow chart

In order to ensure the translation quality of the platform, students are required to pass a proficiency test before entering the platform and provide translation certificates. Since the salary is related to the accuracy of the first draft translation, students will be more responsible for the translation and improve their translation ability. At the same time, by reviewing the first draft of students' translation, teachers can gain practical experience and find problems in the translation of the majority of MTI students, so as to carry out teaching reform and improve the quality of translation teaching.

The personnel department is mainly responsible for staff recruitment and performance appraisal. The technical department is responsible for the initial platform construction and the later maintenance and update of the platform. The marketing department is responsible for market development, platform promotion. Online activities including the creation of WeChat official accounts, editing and sending of tweets, and advertising, while offline activities include negotiating cooperation with companies, holding publicity meetings in schools, etc.

This project adopts a three-level management model (see Figure 2), which is oriented by student groups, and each department has a division of labor and collaboration, and clear responsibilities, which is conducive to improving the overall work efficiency and ultimately creating an efficient and dynamic business operation model.

Figure 2: management model

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(3) Industry Competition Analysis

With the strengthening of international exchanges, people's demand for translation services continues to increase, and the translation market is also booming. Coupled with the development of technology, many part-time translation platforms have emerged in the Chinese market, such as "woordee.com" (a translation platform under the Shi Yi Bao), "Wittrans.com" and "easytep.com"(platforms under Alibaba) and so on. But these platforms have a low penetration rate in the student market, and the quality of translation varies. Compared with aforementioned translation platforms, the translation cloud platform established in this study has the following competitive advantages: a) Distinctive features. This project provides business translation services, which is more professional; b) Teamwork. Translation tasks are carried out in the form of translation projects, which is no longer a single translator's "single fight", but between teams; c) Stable Sources. The number of translators are stable, because translators are mainly college students and graduate students with business background, and it is increasing year by year, providing companies with more choices; d) Price advantage. Translators are mainly college students and postgraduates, and the project is carried out in a teamwork manner, which not only achieves price concessions, but also guarantees quality.

V. RESULTS

(1) Organization and Management Training

According to the plan, the team will hold two departmental meetings a month to summarize the results and deficiencies of each stage, and plan the tasks for the next stage. The team regularly holds training lectures and invites professors in the field of translation to provide professional guidance and teaching, thereby effectively improving the translation capabilities of team members and strengthening the cohesion of the team. In terms of performance appraisal, we strictly follow the monthly appraisal and appraise the translation of members' manuscripts in that month. Performance appraisal has played a positive role in guiding team members' enthusiasm for clocking in and participation in meetings.

(2) Website Construction

The website framework, style design, color matching and other aspects is designed to be close to users. The website has a display function and an online order function. The display content mainly includes five sections: team introduction, service items, results display, translation team and news information. In the team introduction, the client can learn more about the team's background, culture, organizational structure, direction and goals; in the service project, the client can have a preliminary understanding of the business content and related quotations to facilitate their follow-up consultation or order; The display module will select past excellent translation works so that customers can intuitively experience the high-quality translation level of the team; in addition, customers can also know the composition of the team's translators and related introductions of excellent translators in the translation team section; The news and information interface will not only update industry information regularly so that customers and team members can keep abreast of industry developments, but also report internal news in a timely manner to show customers the progress made by the team. If customers want to know more about the team, they can click "Contact Us" to consult manual customer service online, or place an order directly through manual customer service without using a third-party communication platform, making transactions more standardized and convenient.

(3) Official Account Construction

The team will also release daily bilingual translation and promotion of some activities through the official account platform. The content covers economy, technology, music, film and television, etc. In order to give full play to the role of the platform and achieve simultaneous promotion and order acceptance, the team uses the official account's dialog box to customize the menu. We set up two columns of "Translation Summary" and "Contact Us" in the menu column of the official account. Customers can click to understand the team's previous work results and the team's cooperation contact information at any time. Also we add the same online customer service and student order functions as the website to the official account. After the construction of the website is completed, related items will be added to the menu, and the customer can click according to their needs, and the mobile phone will automatically jump to the required information page. Since then, the official account is not just a learning platform, the team will work to build the official account into an important platform for publicizing the company's image and establishing business contacts.

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(4) Business Term Database Construction

The construction of a business term database is conducive to the management of business terms, thereby ensuring the consistency of context and improving translation efficiency. This project will first build a business term database based on the team's preliminary business translation results, combined with the collected data. In the early stage, the team studied the process of terminology database construction, striving to gain a general understanding of the terminology database construction method without the help of relevant technical personnel. The team divides the work, extracts, organizes and categorizes the terms in the previous business translation tasks. Later, from the translator's works and company descriptions, we will sort out a wider range of business categories, including transportation, tourism, culture and entertainment, sports, education, medical and health, postal and telecommunications, catering and accommodation, and business finance.

(5) Expected Translation Results

It is expected to complete translation tasks with high quality, meet customer needs and actively expand translation tasks. The tasks are not limited to translation in the business field, but also involve daily life, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, IT and other fields. Therefore, the number of translators has also been increased accordingly. Through the platform, while improving students' own translation ability, it also allows students to extend their knowledge and improve their practical ability.

VI. CONCLUSION

Translation practice can enable students to understand the translation process, gain practical experience in translation, enhance students' professional translation ability and translation technology application ability, and ensure the further healthy development of MTI. With the rapid development of Internet technology today, building an online translation practice platform with high efficiency, fast feedback and strong interaction not only solves the problem of MTI students' difficulty in translation practice to a certain extent, but also meets the part-time needs of college students. Most importantly, the construction of the platform is initiated by students, with the background of "Internet +", and serving students as the orientation. It responds to the call of the Chinese government to encourage college students to start their own businesses, and combines entrepreneurship, part-time work and practice to demonstrate the positive role played by college students in the trend of "mass entrepreneurship and innovation".

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